

Samarium diiodide promoted reductive cyclization of nitrodisulfides with nitriles : A new route to benzothiazoles

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Manuscript received 26 December 2000, accepted 15 January 2001

Benzothiazole derivatives are prepared via reductive cyclization of nitrodisulfides with nitriles promoted by SmI₂ under mild and neutral conditions.

Benzothiazoles are very important and useful compounds in organic synthesis and pharmaceutical chemistry¹. Many methods have been introduced for preparing benzothiazole derivatives². Many of these suffered from harsh conditions, such as high reaction temperatures, strongly acidic or basic medium and prolonged reaction times. Here we report a convenient method for the preparation of benzothiazoles.

The Kagan's reagent, samarium diiodide³ (SmI₂) has been extensively investigated in synthetic chemistry⁴⁻⁶. As we know esters and nitriles are stable in the THF solution of SmI₂, while nitro group and sulfur-sulfur bond are very sensitive to this reagent^{5,6}. Recently we have reported⁷ that amidines could be synthesized via the intermolecular reductive cyclization of nitro compounds and nitriles promoted by SmI₂. Here we considered of a similar reaction could take place between nitrodisulfides and nitriles in the present of SmI₂.

Results and Discussion

When a mixture of nitrodisulfides **1** and nitriles **2** was added to the THF solution of SmI₂ at room temperature under a nitrogen atmosphere, it was found that the deep blue color of SmI₂ solution disappeared gradually; the intermolecular reductive cyclization reaction proceeded readily and the desired products benzothiazoles **3** could be obtained with satisfactory yields (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Table 1 summarized our results on the reaction of nitrodisulfides with nitriles promoted by SmI₂. In this reaction aromatic nitriles could react with nitrodisulfides to afford the desired benzothiazoles (**3a-q**) in moderate to high yields. However, aliphatic nitriles (**3o-q**, except for benzyl cyanide) failed to react with nitrodisulfides to give the products **3** under the similar conditions, even under low temperature or reflux conditions. On the other hand, when MeOH (0.2 ml) was added to the reaction mixture (nitrosulfides and nitriles), it was found that under the same reaction conditions, no benzothiazoles **3** could be obtained.

Table 1. Preparation of benzothiazoles (**3a-q**) promoted by SmI₂

Compd. no.	X	R	Time h	Yield ^a % ^a	m.p. °C
3a	H	C ₆ H ₅	2	75	110-112 (lit. ^{2a} 113-114)
	H	C ₆ H ₅	24	0 ^b	
b	H	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	2	80	83-85 (lit. ^{2b} 85-86)
c	H	<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	2	81	119-121 (lit. ^{2b} 121-122)
d	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	4	67	115-117 (lit. ^{2a} 117-118)
e	H	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	6	53	144-145 (lit. ^{2a} 146-147)
f	H	2,6-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	10	42	86-88 (lit. ^{2a} 87-90)
g	H	3,4-(OCH ₂ O)C ₆ H ₃	2	71	122-123 (lit. ^{2c} 125)
h	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	4	45	112-113 (lit. ^{2d} 112)
i	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	2	64	138-140 (lit. ^{2a} 140-141)
j	Cl	<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	2	70	147-148 (lit. ^{2e} 149-151)
k	Cl	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	4	61	152-154 (lit. ^{2a} 155-156)
l	Cl	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	6	55	198-201 (lit. ^{2a} 199)
m	Cl	2-furyl	2	62	121-123 (lit. ^{2f} 122)
n	Cl	3,4-(OCH ₂ O)C ₆ H ₃	2	69	172-173 (lit. ^{2f} 173)
o	H	CH ₃	24	0 ^c	-
p	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ CH ₂	24	0 ^c	-
q	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH=CH	24	0 ^c	-

^aIsolated yield based on nitrodisulfides. ^bMeOH (0.2 ml) was added to the mixture, no product **3a** was obtained even under 0, 25 or 70°. ^cNo product **3** was detected.

Note

Scheme 2

Though the detailed mechanism of the reaction has not been clear yet, the benzothiazole formation may be described as shown⁷ in Scheme 2.

According to Scheme 2, a nitrodisulfide **1** by treatment of SmI_2 can produce a radical **A** which attacks the nitriles to form intermediates **B**. The active intermediates **B** by treatment with SmI_2 afford the benzothiazoles **3**. The aromatic nitriles can react with radical **A** to form the stable intermediates **B**, while aliphatic nitriles can not give the stable intermediates **B** due to their inductive effect, so no product could be detected under the same conditions.

In conclusion, a new route to benzothiazoles via intermolecular reductive cyclization of nitrodisulfides with nitriles promoted by SmI_2 has been developed, the advantages of which are accessible starting materials, mild reaction conditions, convenient manipulation and good yields.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran was freshly distilled from sodium/benzophenone ketyl before use. Metallic samarium and other chemicals were commercially available and used as such. The reaction was performed in a Schlenk type glass apparatus and under a nitrogen atmosphere. ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a Bruker 80 MHz instrument using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard, IR spectra on a PE-683 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a HP 5989B MS spectrometer. Microanalysis was carried out on a EA 1101 instrument.

General procedure: A mixture solution of nitrodisulfides **1** (0.5 mmol) and nitriles **2** (1 mmol) in anhydrous THF (3 ml) was added dropwise to SmI_2 (7 mmol) in dry THF (30 ml) at room temperature. The deep blue color of the mixture gradually changed to yellow, after being stirred for a given period of time (Table 1). The reaction was monitored by TLC, then quenched with HCl (0.1 mol dm^{-3} ; 3 ml) and extracted with ether ($3 \times 30 \text{ ml}$). The product was isolated with the usual procedure and purified by preparative TLC using ethyl acetate and cyclohexane (1 :

7) as eluant. All the products were characterised : **3a**^{2a}, ν_{max} 3010, 1620, 1580, 1500, 755, 740, 690 cm^{-1} , δ 7.65–7.15 (9H, m, ArH); **3b**^{2b}, ν_{max} 3015, 2980, 1620, 1580, 1375, 840, 750 cm^{-1} , δ 7.67–6.96 (8H, m, ArH), 2.36 (3H, s, CH_3); **3c**^{2b}, ν_{max} 3010, 2972, 1615, 1575, 1500, 1380, 1250, 1050, 823, 745 cm^{-1} , δ 7.83–7.06 (8H, m, ArH), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3); **3d**^{2a}, ν_{max} 3013, 1620, 1550, 1450, 840, 760, 680 cm^{-1} , δ 7.87–7.08 (8H, m, ArH); **3e**^{2a}, ν_{max} 3020, 1618, 1575, 1500, 1450, 890, 830, 756, 740, 700 cm^{-1} , δ 7.70–7.18 (7H, m, ArH); **3f**^{2a}, ν_{max} 3030, 1622, 1580, 1500, 1450, 780, 753, 695 cm^{-1} , δ 7.66–7.32 (7H, m, ArH); **3g**^{2c}, ν_{max} 3010, 2780, 1615, 1570, 1500, 1460, 1150, 880, 750, 690 cm^{-1} , δ 7.63–6.73 (7H, m, ArH), 5.93 (2H, s, OCH_2O); **3h**^{2d}, ν_{max} 3015, 2930, 2840, 1600, 1560, 1475, 760, 740, 690 cm^{-1} , δ 7.57–6.96 (9H, m, ArH), 4.12 (2H, s, CH_2); **3i**^{2a}, ν_{max} 3018, 1625, 1500, 1450, 760, 740, 690 cm^{-1} , δ 7.83–7.19 (8H, m, ArH); **3j**^{2e}, ν_{max} 3020, 2980, 1620, 1580, 1500, 1380, 1250, 1060, 820, 760, 690 cm^{-1} , δ 7.81–6.74 (7H, m, ArH), 3.74 (3H, s, OCH_3); **3k**^{2a}, ν_{max} 3010, 1620, 1570, 1500, 870, 830, 756, 720, 680 cm^{-1} , δ 7.81–7.07 (7H, m, ArH); **3l**^{2a}, ν_{max} 3020, 1615, 1580, 1500, 1450, 880, 830, 715, 680 cm^{-1} , δ 7.76–7.16 (6H, m, ArH); **3m**^{2f}, ν_{max} 3020, 1620, 1570, 1500, 1250, 1080, 870, 825, 720, 680 cm^{-1} , δ 7.73–6.38 (4H, m, ArH), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3); **3n**^{2f}, ν_{max} 3015, 2780, 1625, 1550, 1475, 1250, 1060, 870, 825, 740, 690 cm^{-1} , δ 7.80–6.57 (6H, m, ArH), 5.95 (2H, s, OCH_2O).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the National Science Foundation of China and the NSF of Zhejiang province for financial support.

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